

The International Centre for Study of Bengal Art (বঙ্গীয় শিল্পকলা চর্চার আন্তর্জাতিক কেন্দ্র) is a specialized research and resource Centre on the Art History and Archaeology of Bangladesh and South and Southeast Asia. One of the important objectives of this Centre is to create academic alliances with various friendly countries through the heritage study of Bengal. The Board of Trustees of this Centre has decided to dedicate several issues of the annual research journal, i.e. *Journal of Bengal Art*, to the names of living foreign Bengal Art researchers who are associated with this Centre in terms of contributing research articles in the *Journal of Bengal Art* and participating in the conferences organized by the Centre. In that light, Vol. 25 of the *Journal of Bengal Art* is dedicated to the renowned art historian and archaeologist Dr. R. Nagaswamy of India. Vol. 26 has been dedicated to German art historian Dr. Claudine Bautze Picron. Vol. 27 has been dedicated to three famous Austrian art historians, Professor Dr. Andria Loseries, Dr. Heinrich Poell and Dr. Gerald Kozicz. In the same vein, the present issue is dedicated to architect and art historian of Thailand DR. CHOTIMA CHATURAWONG. It should be noted that they are all engaged in research of South and Southeast Asian art, but we credit them for their love and special attention to the study of Bengal art. We believe that their research and publications on Bengal art and archaeology will reveal much information on Bengal art history and archaeology. We hope that this volume will serve as an academic memento to the Thailand-Bangladesh friendship. ICSBA's academic initiatives will continue to foster friendship with foreign scholars who engage in Bengal art research.

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Dedicated to
Chotima Chaturawong

28

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JOINTLY EDITED
BY

MD. MOSHARRAF HOSSAIN
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বঙ্গীয় শিল্পকলা চর্চার আন্তর্জাতিক কেন্দ্র
THE INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR STUDY OF BENGAL ART
DHAKA, BANGLADESH

EDITOR'S NOTE: THAILAND-BANGLADESH RELATIONSHIP

The historical ties between Bangladesh and Thailand are largely due to maritime connections, piety, and human behavioral patterns that have been continuing since a distant past. It is more or less a geographical gift as both countries are located in a horizon of such Southeast Asian pan-Pacific territorial hub which has been witnessing the same cultural ups and downs 4th centuries long. Sea routes were vital for facilitating trade and negotiation, fostering strong ties between Bengal and regions such as Siam (present-day Thailand). The discovery of archaeological artefacts, such as seals with Kharoshtri-Brahmi scripts and pottery, in Southeast Asian regions provides tangible proof of these ancient trade and cultural links originating from Bengal. Bengali architectural styles and bronze art, particularly from the Pala School of Art, influenced the art and temple architecture found in Southeast Asian regions.

Maritime trade between Thailand and Bengal is evinced by examining cultural materials from the fourth century BCE to the fourth century CE found in archaeological sites of the region and places. Arduous efforts by archaeologists made over the last four decades have revealed a rich collection of artefacts, each pregnant with startling revelations of Thailand and Bengal's past. Quite a few archaeological materials help us to ascertain the maritime trade network between Thailand and Bengal from the fourth century BCE to the fourth century CE. Important among these are Northern Black Polished Ware, Rouletted Ware, knobbed ware, stamped Ware, glass and semi-precious stone beads, seals and sealings with Kharosti-Brahmi inscription.

During the first half of the first millennium CE, a mixed script consisting of Kharosti and Brahmi was in use in parts of Bengal. The Kushana merchants from Gandhara and the Oxus regions, whose script was Kharosti (north-western Prakrit), migrated to the lower Ganga Valley in Bengal and settled in Chandraketugarh and the Tamruk region. Gradually, they synthesized their Kharosti and local Brahmi (another form of Prakrit) letters to give rise to a mixed script known as Kharosti-Brahmi. More than 135 inscriptions, either stamped or incised with Kharosti or Brahmi letters or a combination of Kharosti and Brahmi letters, have been found so far on vessels (pots and jars), plaques, and seals during excavations and explorations at various sites in Bengal. Seals have also been reported from Central Thailand and Krabi Province in southern Thailand. Hence, the findings of these seals indicate maritime trade links between Bengal and Thailand.

This is the historical background, but in the present context we see, Thailand and Bangladesh share a strong and growing bilateral relationship such as trade, investment, and cultural exchange. They cooperate through regional bodies like BIMSTEC. Bangladesh views Thailand as a gateway between Southeast and South Asia and aims to enhance connectivity. The relationship has seen augmented high-level visits, official interactions, and more people-to-people contact, especially in tourism and health.

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(Dedicated to Chotima Chaturawong)
(An academic memento of Thailand-Bangladesh Friendship)

Volume 28, 2023

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THE INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR STUDY OF BENGAL ART

গণপ্রজাতন্ত্রী বাংলাদেশ সরকারের সংস্কৃতি বিষয়ক মন্ত্রণালয়ের অর্থায়নে পরিচালিত

বাংলার প্রত্নতত্ত্ব ও শিল্পকলার ইতিহাস বিষয়ক গবেষণা ও রিসোর্স প্রতিষ্ঠান

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ANALYZING THE WARRIORS AND WEAPONRY REPRESENTED ON ANCIENT BUDDHIST TEMPLE TERRACOTTA PLAQUES OF LALMAI-MAINAMATI

Muhammed Shohrab Uddin, Md. Abdul Momin and Nazmul Alam Ridoy

Abstract: The history of ancient Bengal is primarily focused on the conquering and expansion of the kingdom by rulers. The state's military power has played a principal role in expanding its borders, conquering neighboring states, and enhancing its security. Various historical books and literature have documented the military forces of ancient Bengal's rulers. Terracotta plaques are one of the most important archaeological findings in the context of Bengal, and they can provide a strong foundation for the history of the military power of ancient Bengal in the light of evidence from archaeological research. The discovery of numerous terracotta plaques in ancient and early historical archaeological sites in diverse parts of Bengal is also a significant find. These plaques display a variety of aspects of society. The pictures on the terracotta plaques depict the real-life situation of society at that time. As a result, these artifacts are considered significant sources in historical writing. The ancient terracotta plaques discovered in the Lalmai-Mainamati region depict war scenes, warriors, and various types of weapons; through analysis of the terracotta plaques, the present study discusses the weaponry used in the battlefields of ancient Bengal.

Introduction

Lalmai Mainamati has a prominent place in the history of ancient Bengal. The Lalmai Mainamati area is located high above sea level and measures approximately 18 km in length, with numerous low-altitude mounds scattered throughout an area roughly 3 km wide. This region was once part of southeast Bengal's ancient Samatata. Devaparvata was a place that held the honor of being Samatata's capital in several times. According to historians, this location, identified as Devaparvata, was part of the rugged terrain of prehistoric Lalmai Mainamati. Numerous kings have ruled the region for a long time, according to various historical sources. Thus far, Alam has named 34 rulers from seven dynasties in its favor (Alam, 1976). This planned city saw the construction of numerous Buddhist monasteries, temples, stupas, and other religious structures. The construction of military bases during World War II completely destroyed many of these ancient structures. The Department of Archaeology discovered 55 archaeological sites, and they declared 20 sites as protected (Alam, 1976) and excavated 11 later to unearth ancient monuments. Numerous terracotta plaques are among the artifacts discovered at these sites. These terracotta plaques exhibit a variety of images, including religious narratives, social life, landscapes, and conceptual scenarios. Furthermore, these terracotta plaques showcase